

Modelling and analysis of a compression/resorption heat pump system with a zeotropic mixture of Acetone/CO₂

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Abstract: Industrial processes represent one of the most energy-consuming activities, which are related to fossil fuel utilization and the growing environmental problems. In this way, the heat waste energy recovery has been presented as an efficient solution, to take advantage of low-grade residual heat, where the compressor-resorption heat pump technology has proven to achieve high-temperature levels with a considerable Coefficient of Performance. However, known working fluids such as hydrofluorocarbons represents an environmental hazard due to its Global Warming potential, these have been replaced by natural fluids such as ammonia, but they also have disadvantages like its toxicity. In this way, the CO₂ is an available waste heat compound product of fossil combustions, therefore, this research is based on the utilization of novel fluids such as the zeotropic mixture of CO₂/Acetone as an eco-friendly working fluid with low Global Warming Potential.. Even more, the utilization of CO₂/Acetone represents the opportunity to explore the utilization of low-grade residual heat that sometimes is not used in further applications. In this sense, the modelling of the binary vapor-liquid equilibria of the mixture CO₂/Acetone has been performed based on a thermodynamic model using the Peng-Robinson equation regarding the conditions of pressure, temperature, and concentration of the fluids for operational industry applications. The modelling of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle is based on the mass and energy balance for each component with Engineering Equation Solver software (EES). In this way, the adjustment of equilibria for the mixture determinates the maximum average square deviation of 4.28 % and 8.70 % for a temperature range between 291 to 303 K and 333 to 393 K. The concentration of CO₂ from 20 % to 50 % showed that the increasing molar fraction delivers a more efficient cycle, even reaching a coefficient of performance of 3 for a difference of 0.2 between the global concentration of CO₂ and the poor solution, and a 20 °C temperature difference between source and sink. Even more, the COP obtained in the simulation was not affected by variations of steam mass flow rate and it was proven that the mathematical model proposed has a correlation with the literature

Keywords: compression, resorption; heat pump; zeotropic mixture; Peng-Robinson; waste heat

Nomenclature	x	Molar fraction on liquid phase
<i>Acronyms</i>	y	Molar fraction on vapour phase
PR Peng-Robinson	V_m	Molar volume
VLE Vapor-Liquid Equilibrium	MW	Molecular weight
<i>Subscripts</i>	m	Parameter in the function of acentric factor of Pitzer
w Acentric factor of Pitzer	α	Parameter in the function of reduced temperature
P_{crit} Critical Pressure	C	Peneloux correction factor
T_{crit} Critical Temperature	P	Pressure
Z Compressibility Factor	T_R	Reduced Temperature
ρ Density	T	Temperature
h Enthalpy	\emptyset	Transience of the phase
R Ideal gas constant	v	Vapour phase
l Liquid phase		
\dot{m} Mass Flow		

<i>Units</i>		$g \times mol^{-1}$	Molecular weight
$cal \times (molK)^{-1}$	Constant coefficient of gases	<i>Bar</i>	Pressure
$kg \times s^{-1}$	Mass flow	$cm^3 \times gmol^{-1}$	Vapour

1. Introduction

Regarding the global energy consumption that has as the main source the utilization of fossil fuels, the problems related to energy and the environment has become prominent, where, the industrial processes in China represents one of the most consuming energy activity, having a 71,1% share of the primary energy consumption [1]. Even more, regarding the heating needs in the building and industry sectors, 75 % of the final energy is used for this purpose, and in European countries such as the Netherlands, the chemical and refinery industries produce over 100 PJ of waste energy per year, facts that make consider that more efficient use of waste energy could have a major effect on energy consumption and therefore carbon footprint [2]. In this sense, as an industrial heat waste recovery solution heat pumps have improved the energy efficiency of industrial processes by taking advantage of the low-grade waste heat recovery [3]. Whereas high-temperature heat pumps as an alternative for enhancing energy efficiency have reached large temperature lifts over 80 °C [4] making it a technology that within its reaches can also provide space heating [5] and consequently contribute as a solution for energy and environmental pollution problems [6]. Furthermore, research to improve the efficiency of thermal systems has been developed by experimenting with different refrigerants to analyse the thermodynamic behaviour of the operation parameters [7], in this sense, the heat pumps technology has advanced and classified as mechanical heat pumps and absorption heat pumps (AHP), where, the first type uses high Global Warming Potential (GWP) refrigerants, while the AHP works with eco-friendly fluid [3], is based on a vapour-absorption cycle [8] and agrees with the international protocols implemented to reduce the release of the greenhouse gases into the atmosphere [9], even more, the heat pumps can also reduce the energy consumption since its development has reached different industrial applications [10]. In this sense, considering the worldwide interest in solving problems such as global warming, heat pump technologies offers a practical solution to offset the greenhouse emissions by recirculating the environment and waste heat from the industrial processes [11]. In this way, it has been studied the different industrial sector that produces useful heat, such as the production of paper, food, chemicals, automotive, metal, textile, wood, and other, where it has been found that processes release temperatures between the 20°C and 200°C [12], therefore, the heat pump technology has been catalogued as a heating capacity increasing system, efficient and stable [13].

In this sense, the AHP has been used with several heat sources such as exhaust gases, gas burners, and solar power among others, where the utilization of this heat has been applied to space heating, water heating, drying, industrial pre-heating and industrial distillation [14]. However, this technology is limited by the thermodynamic behaviour of the working fluids and the resistance of its components to reach elevated temperatures useful in industrial processes. Nevertheless, the absorption heat pumps cannot provide temperature lifts, and in this way, resorption systems are considered an alternative to the conventional vapour compression pumps, even more, an advantage of this technology is the compatibility to use friendly refrigerants such as water, ammonia and CO₂ [15]. In this sense, traditional heat pump systems are composed by a compressor, expansion valve and a condenser, but a compressor resorption heat pump (CRHP) has a resorber-desorber instead of a condenser and evaporator, allowing to achieve high-temperature levels with relatively good Coefficient Of Performance (COP) [16] that are enhanced by the application of these hybrid systems [17]. Since the absorption-resorption is a non-isothermal process where the entropy generation decreases regarding the temperature difference [18], where, the relevance of a high COP responds to the fact that only if this is greater or equal to the energy

1 factor of an electric generator, the heat pump could emit less carbon dioxide compared to the traditional
2 heating systems [19]. In this sense, the CRHP is also known as an absorption-resorption heat pump, has
3 been described as a promising application when low temperature is used for space heating [20], the
4 interest in this system has grown in theoretical and experimental aspects, delivering successful
5 implementations on commercial units [21] which is the typical application due to their large size [22],
6 even more, showing to be an appropriate alternative to the conventional heat pumps considering that
7 has limitations like the temperature of discharge in the compressor [23]. In this way, authors like
8 Gudjonsdottir & Infante Ferreira, have concluded that the CRHP technologies are a clear option to
9 upgrade waste heat streams [24]. Moreover, the CRHP system can be found as an evaporator-condenser
10 system that can be integrated with different heat sources such as waste heat, gas engine, Organic
11 Rankine Cycle and microturbine, where the resorption subsystem can work with LiBr-H₂O, LiCl-H₂O
12 and NH₃-H₂O and the compression subsystem may use R134a, R410A, NH₃, low- GWP HFO
13 refrigerants, CO₂ [25]. On the other hand, the working pairs for desorption/resorption systems are fluids
14 that consume or produce heat, with the requirements of having good thermal properties on the working
15 conditions such as thermal storage, conductivity, stability heat transfer coefficient, along with other
16 characteristics like non-corrosive, non-toxic, etc. [26].

17 However, some vapour-compression technologies use potent greenhouse gases refrigerants such as
18 hydrofluorocarbons (HFC), but can be replaced by natural fluids that reduce the environmental impact,
19 in this sense, the compression resorption systems can use zeotropic binary mixtures that have the
20 advantage as a working fluid that produces a reduction on vapour pressures compared to other volatile
21 fluids [27]. Even more, zeotropic mixtures have important boiling temperature differences, whereas
22 mixtures of ammonia-water have been studied but its toxicity has led to the research of other mixtures
23 such as the carbon dioxide and ammonia mixture, where, the mixtures of ammonia-water has been
24 studied on absorption-compression heat pumps, allowing to conclude that is a promising and efficient
25 alternative on the utilization of high temperatures for industrial applications [27]. On the other hand,
26 the CO₂-based zeotropic mixtures have drawn the attention in the field since it can integrate different
27 benefits and enhance the Coefficient of performance of the system [28]. In this way, several studies that
28 include numerical simulations as experimental proposals have shown results with increments on the
29 COP by analysing the combinations of CO₂ and hydrocarbons [29]. Furthermore, regarding the superior
30 performance of CO₂ as a supercritical fluid and the characteristics of being inexpensive, stable,
31 abundant [30], and considering the low COP of vapour compression cycles using CO₂, experiments
32 were carried out by circulating the CO₂ with a low volatile absorption liquid as a co-fluid [31], taking
33 into account that CO₂ has been catalogued as a natural refrigerant with great potential for its
34 environmental and thermodynamic characteristics on experimental research of transcritical heat
35 pumping cycles [32]. In this sense, Groll & Kruse 1992, proposed the utilization of acetone as the
36 absorbent [33] resulting in modelling with a good agreement with the experimental result [31], also,
37 Mozurkewich et al., simulated a refrigeration cycle for a co-circulation and wet compression of CO₂
38 and absorbing co-fluids such as N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone, Neopentylglycol diacetate, γ -Butyrolactone
39 and Acetone, concluding that the maximum theoretical COP is obtained when the entropy generation
40 rate is minimized and the best mixture is CO₂-Acetone[34], also, when compared the miscibility of the
41 CO₂ with other fluids such as toluene and monochlorobenzene in an analysis of pressure-density-
42 temperature near critical states, the acetone proved to be the best for CO₂[35]. In this way, the carbon
43 dioxide (CO₂) is a non-toxic compound that can be found as gas in atmospheric conditions of 1bar and
44 a temperature of 20°C, and shares 0.03% of the atmospheric volume, while a liquid phase is present in
45 a temperature range of -56.6°C to 31.1°C at a minimum pressure of 5.2 bar [36]. On the other hand,
46 acetone is a solvent with a boiling and fusion temperature of 56.2°C and -95.4°C respectably, it has a
47 solubility on the water of 0.791 kg×l⁻¹ and vapour pressure of 180 mmHg at 20°C [37].

48 The mixture of the CO₂/Acetone has been studied by several authors under different conditions, where
49 the modelling of the binary vapour-liquid equilibria can be correlated by using the Peng-Robinson
50 equation [38]. In this sense, the research of Han et al. showed an equilibrium of the vapour mixture on

1 a pressure interval of 2.36 MPa to 11.77 MPa, a temperature between 333.15 K to 393.15 K and a molar
2 fraction of CO₂ of 0.32 to 0.92 [39]. In the thermodynamic diagram of equilibrium liquid-vapour of the
3 binary mixtures of CO₂ with acetone and pentanes made by Hsieh & Vrabec, [40] the pressure studied
4 was from 5.13MPa to 11.8MPa, temperatures of 313.15, 333 and 353 K with a molar fraction of CO₂
5 of 0.48 to 0.85. On the other hand, the research of Chiu et al., [41] studied the isothermal vapour-liquid
6 equilibrium (VLE) phase boundaries of the mixtures CO₂ with ethanol and CO₂ with acetone at
7 temperatures from 291.15K to 313.15K with different compositions that include molar fractions of CO₂
8 from 0.19 to 0.98 for pressures from 0.72 MPa to 7.95 MPa, is important to point out that these
9 investigations indicate that the acetone is an effective absorbent of CO₂ and has the best miscibility for
10 CO₂ compared to other absorbents. Moreover, in recent studies Ramírez-Ramos et al., proved that the
11 CO₂ can show good miscibility and solubility with acetone at temperatures of 283.15K to 383.15K in a
12 composition of 0.04 to 0.85 CO₂ mole fraction for pressure up to 8.7MPa, showing a steady VLE [42].
13 On the other hand, regarding the modelling of the compression-absorption heat pump systems, several
14 researchers have used computational methods to validate the thermodynamic processes in different
15 models, these software uses an iterative procedure to solve equations and converge on a numerical
16 solution [43]. In this sense, the research of Jensen et al., made a thermodynamic model the of an
17 ammonia-water compression-absorption heat pump system, calculating the properties of the mixture by
18 the software along with the transport properties following the equations and correlations referenced in
19 the literature, and using an iteration of 50 steps for the desorber and the absorber, allowing to
20 determinate the pitch point temperature differences [44]. On the other hand, Liu et al. used the Aspen
21 plus software to study a mixture of a high-temperature CAHP waste heat recovery system and declared
22 that a COP with a relative error of 0.54% compared to the literature, meaning reliable results and useful
23 information [45]. In this way, this investigation proposes the study of the zeotropic mixture of Acetone-
24 CO₂, considering the low GWP and its non-hazardous nature compared to other much more studied
25 working fluids, to be used as an alternative eco-friendly working fluid for compression-resorption heat
26 pump systems with low thermal energy that has a lack of research, on industrial applications.
27 Furthermore, in the medium term this contribution can constitute a basis for the studies regarding the
28 recovery of residual heat at low temperatures (40 to 60 °C), and be able to produce a thermal repower
29 at useful temperatures (80 to 120 °C) for the same industry. Even more, regarding the bibliographical
30 research and with aid of the Aspen software [46], the present research has the objective of modelling
31 the behaviour of the mixture CO₂/Acetone following the Peng-Robinson equations regarding the
32 pressure, temperature, and concentration for the application of a CRHP on the industrial sector, meaning
33 the simulation of an alternative working fluid. In this sense, this work establishes a parametric analysis
34 for different operative conditions that allows obtaining a range of limitations to apply the binary mixture
35 to the industry and opening the path for further experimental research based on the results obtained.

36 2. Method and Materials

37

38 The bibliographical research allowed to analyse the different methods that have been used to calculate
39 the thermodynamic properties of the binary mixtures of Acetone/CO₂, in this sense, it has been found
40 that due to the mathematical relative simplicity the authors has used the state equations of Soave Redlich
41 Kwong, Patel-Teja and Peng-Robinson (PR) [47]. In a general way, the PR equation shows better
42 approximations between calculated data and experimental values, demonstrating lower deviations in
43 the results presented. The researches of Hsieh & Vrabec, [40] and Han et al. (2005) [39], are part of the
44 studies that recommend the utilization of the state equation of PR to determine the VLE and other
45 characteristics of the acetone/CO₂ mixture, making this the chosen method to be used. The properties
46 are determined so that the same properties can be used in the simulation of the compression/resorption
47 heat pump cycle. That is, to study the CO₂/acetone mixture as the working fluid for this type of cycle.

48

2.1. Thermodynamic properties model

The PR method allows to calculate of the VLE, enthalpy, entropy and density of the mixture, the state equation [47] is expressed in equations (1) to (5) as:

$$P = \frac{RT}{v - b} - \frac{a}{v(v + b) + b(v - b)} \quad (1)$$

Where:

$$a = 0.45724 \frac{R^2 T_{crit}^2}{P_{crit}} \alpha \quad (2)$$

$$b = 0.07780 \frac{RT_{crit}}{P_{crit}} \quad (3)$$

$$\sqrt{\alpha} = 1 + m(1 - \sqrt{T_r}) \quad (4)$$

$$m = 0.37464 + 1.54226w - 0.26992w^2 \quad (5)$$

2.2. Peng-Robinson equation for mixtures

The PR equation has been declared, however, for this research the fluid that will be studied is a compound of Acetone and CO₂. For this matter, the properties of the materials are displayed in table 1 and the PR equation for mixtures is expressed in equation (6), where the Pitzer's acentric factor (w) represents the spherical symmetry of the CO₂ and the acetone as a molecular force field [48]

Table 1. Compound properties[49]

Parameter	Unit	CO ₂	Acetone
P_{crit}	bar	72.8	46.4
T_{crit}	K	304.2	508.1
v	cm ³ x gmol ⁻¹	94	209
w	-	0.225	0.309
MW	g x mol ⁻¹	44.01	58.08

$$P = \frac{RT}{(v - b_m)} - \frac{a_m}{v(v + b_m) + b_m(v - b_m)} \quad (6)$$

For the mixture of CO₂/Acetone it has been used the classic rules of Van der Waals (Klein) that describe the characteristic parameters of a_m and b_m as follows in equations (7)-(8):

$$a_m = a_1 x_1^2 + a_2 x_2^2 + 2x_1 x_2 a_{12} \quad (7)$$

$$b_m = b_1 x_1^2 + b_2 x_2^2 + x_1 x_2 b_{12} \quad (8)$$

Corresponding the sub-index (1) to CO₂ and (2) for acetone, the interaction parameters a_{12} ; b_{12} are calculated with equations (9)-(10), where k_{12} is the parameter of binary interaction of the mixture.

$$a_{12} = \sqrt{a_1 \times a_2} \times (1 - k_{12}) \quad (9)$$

$$b_{12} = \frac{1}{2}(b_1 + b_2) \quad (10)$$

1 Following the PR state equation in terms of the compressibility factor, equations (11)-(13) corresponds
 2 to a cubic formulation which resolution that has been taken from the book of thermodynamics by Klein
 3 & Nellis, 2011 [50] as follows:

$$Z^3 - (1 - B)Z^2 + (A - 3B^2 - 2B)Z - (AB - B^2 - B^3) = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$A = \frac{a_m P}{R^2 T^2} \quad (12)$$

$$B = \frac{a_m P}{RT} \quad (13)$$

7 Likewise, the determination of the VLE along with other properties requires the parameter of binary
 8 interaction of the mixture in terms of temperature pressure and concentration, which are obtained from
 9 the adjustment of experimental data of the factor K that is calculated as $K=y \times x^{-1}$ from the previous
 10 studies of Han et al. [39], Hsieh & Vrabec [40], Chiu et al. [41] and Ramírez-Ramos et al. [42]. In this
 11 sense, for the mathematical iterative model based on PR the factor K can be calculated using the
 12 transience of each phase for every fluid as follows in equation (14):

$$K_i = \frac{\phi_i^l}{\phi_i^v} = \frac{l_i}{v_i} \quad (14)$$

14 The calculation of K must be compared and repeated with the initial K_i value until it has a tolerate
 15 proximity showing convergence in the value. Furthermore, the transience ϕ of the compound is
 16 calculated with equation (15), where the terms AA and BB corresponding to combination parameters
 17 are calculated with equations (16-17) and as follows.

$$\ln \phi_i = (BB)_i(Z_i - 1) - \ln(Z_i - B) - \frac{A}{2\sqrt{2}B} ((AA)_i - (BB)_i) \ln \left[\frac{Z_i + (\sqrt{2} + 1)B}{Z_i - (\sqrt{2} - 1)B} \right] \quad (15)$$

$$(AA)_i = \frac{2}{\alpha a_m} \left[\sum_i^2 (a\alpha)_i \right] \quad (16)$$

$$(BB)_i = \frac{b_i}{b_m} \quad (17)$$

21 Furthermore, the transience of the compound in the liquid phase is calculated with equation (18), where
 22 the term $\phi_{i(T,P_{sat})}^l$ refers to the transience of the compound in saturation conditions and V_l corresponds
 23 to the molar volume of a liquid phase. On the other hand, the transience of the component in the vapour
 24 phase is expressed by equation (19).

$$\phi_i^l = \phi_{i(T,P_{sat})}^l \frac{v_i(p-P_{sat})}{RT} \quad (18)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{\phi_i^v}{P}\right) = Z_i - 1 - \ln(Z_i - B) - \frac{A}{2\sqrt{2}B} \ln\left[\frac{Z_i + (\sqrt{2} + 1)B}{Z_i - (\sqrt{2} - 1)B}\right] \quad (19)$$

Lastly, the cubic model equation of PR proposes the relation between the parameter of binary interaction with the temperature according to the following equation (20):

$$k_{12} = k_1 + k_2 T + \frac{k_3}{T} \quad (20)$$

The coefficients k_1 , k_2 and k_3 were found using a modification in the objective function of the fit of the experimental data using the ASPEN PLUS software [46].

Furthermore, the PR model and the values of binary interaction for different temperatures allows to achieve a graphic of the vapour pressure of the CO₂/Acetone mixture in the function of the molar composition of CO₂. Moreover, the Duhring diagram (PTXY) shows the graph of vapour pressure versus temperature for different concentrations of CO₂ in the liquid phase and vapour phase of the CO₂ / Acetone mixture. The Clausius-Clapeyron equation states that when in a system formed by a pure substance or a mixture with two phases in equilibrium at a temperature T and a pressure P, a temperature change represents a change in pressure for the restoration of equilibrium thermodynamic [51]. In this sense, assuming that the vapour phase is an ideal gas, and that the molar volume of the liquid is negligible compared to the molar volume of the vapour, the so-called Clausius-Clapeyron equation is reached, which describes the vapour pressure of the mixture as a function of temperature, considering an enthalpy of vaporization. The relationship between the change of both magnitudes is given in equation (21) where ΔH_v represents the molar enthalpy of vaporization and its integration under the assumption that ΔH_v is constant in the interval of temperature and pressure resulting in the equation (22).

$$\frac{d \ln P}{dT} = \frac{\Delta H_v}{RT^2} \quad (21)$$

$$\ln P = -\frac{\Delta H_v}{RT} + C \quad (22)$$

Considering ΔH_v as a constant, the graphical representation of $\ln P$ versus $1 \times T^{-1}$ corresponds to a straight line with slope $-\Delta H_v \times R^{-1}$ [51].

Furthermore, the following Fig. 1 represents the logical sequential order that has been followed to determine the properties of the CO₂/acetone mixture. This scheme summarizes the procedure defined in points 2.1 and 2.2.

Figure 1. Logical procedure for the determination of VLE properties of the CO₂/acetone mixture

2.3. Determination of Density of the mixture

Following the state equations, the density of the mixture CO₂/Acetone is determined in the liquid and vapor state. This density is obtained through the compressibility factor Z with the equation (23), where R is the constant of ideal gases with the value of $R=8.314 \text{ J} \times \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$. This factor is calculated for each phase Z_l (liquid) and Z_v (vapor) with the equations (24-25) respectively.

$$Z = \frac{PV_m}{RT} \quad (23)$$

$$V_{ml} = \frac{Z_l RT}{P} = \frac{1}{\rho_l} \quad (24)$$

$$V_{mv} = \frac{Z_v RT}{P} = \frac{1}{\rho_v} \quad (25)$$

1 Furthermore, with the data expressed by Ramírez-Ramos et al., [42], a correlation between the density
 2 of the mixture in the liquid phase with the composition and the temperature is performed, obtaining the
 3 following equation (26) for the molar fraction of CO₂ in the CO₂/Acetone mixture (X_{CO_2}) as a function
 4 of the temperature and the density. Where the terms T_n and ρ_n are expressed by equations (27) and (28)

$$X_{CO_2} = \rho_{00} + (\rho_{10} * T_n) + (\rho_{01} * \rho_n) + (\rho_{20} * T_n^2) + (\rho_{11} * T_n * \rho_n) + (\rho_{02} * \rho_n^2) +$$

$$(\rho_{21} * \rho_n * T_n^2) + (\rho_{12} * T_n * \rho_n^2) + (\rho_{03} * \rho_n^3) \quad (26)$$

$$T_n = \frac{(T - 291.6)}{5.57} \quad (27)$$

$$\rho_n = \frac{(\rho - 864.8)}{34.59} \quad (28)$$

7 Density calculations with the Peng-Robinson equation have been improved using the specific volume
 8 correction factor proposed by Pénélox et al. [52] to the Soave-Redlich-Kwong (SRK) equation. The
 9 correction is specific to each substance and independent of temperature. The authors propose to
 10 generalize the constants used in the correction equation through the Rackett compressibility factor,
 11 ZRA. The Pénélox volume correction factor directly influences the calculation of the molar volume
 12 obtained by the Peng Robinson equation of state and is applied as shown by the equation (29) that
 13 calculates the molar volume correction for the liquid state ($V_{ml_{corr}}$) using the correction factor of
 14 Pénélox (C) that is expressed by equation (30), being C_i the specific correction coefficient for CO₂ (C_1)
 15 and acetone (C_2) that can be calculated by equation (31).

$$V_{ml_{corr}} = V_{ml} - C \quad (29)$$

$$C = \sum_i^2 (X_i C_i) \quad (30)$$

$$C_i = 0.40768 \frac{RT_{crit}}{P_{crit}} (0.29441 - Z_{RA_i}) \quad (31)$$

18 In this sense, the Rackett parameters for CO₂ (Z_{RA_1}) are 0.272 and for acetone (Z_{RA_2}) 0.244 [49]

19 2.4. Calculation of enthalpy and entropy of the mixture CO₂/Acetone

20
 21 The enthalpy of the mixture (h) has been calculated from the enthalpy of the ideal mixture and the
 22 enthalpy of deviation of the mixture is obtained with the Peng-Robinson equation of state expressed in
 23 equation (32). In this way, the enthalpy of an ideal mixture ($h_{idealmix}$) is calculated with equation (33),
 24 which at the same time considers the ideal gas enthalpy of each component, which can be calculated
 25 from the ideal gas heat capacity, $C_{p_i}^o$ by integration as shown in equation (34).

$$h = h_{idealmix} - h_{dev} \quad (32)$$

$$h_{idealmix} = \sum_{i=1}^2 (h_i * x_i) \quad (33)$$

$$h_i = \int C_{p_i}^o * dT \quad (34)$$

1

2 On the other hand, to directly calculate the ideal gas heat capacity of each component it has been used
3 the expression presented by Fouad et al. [53] is displayed in equation (35), where, the expression B ,
4 C , D , E , F are constant coefficients for each component which are displayed in table 2.

$$C_{p_i}^o = B + C \left[\frac{(D/T)}{\text{Sinh}(D/T)} \right]^2 + E \left[\frac{(F/T)}{\text{Cosh}(F/T)} \right]^2 \quad (35)$$

5

6

7 **Table 2.** Constants for CO₂ and Acetone

Coefficients	B	C	D	E	F
	$cal \times (molK)^{-1}$	$cal \times (molK)^{-1}$	K	$cal \times (molK)^{-1}$	K
CO ₂ (1)	14.508	37.979	1709.8	24.296	799.14
Acetone (2)	7.5405	7.5162	1442.7	5.3802	647.50

8

9 Lastly, the expression of the deviation of enthalpy (h_{dev}) for the mixture is calculated using the following
10 equation (36) described by Klein & Nellis, [50], where the expression $B=b_m P \times (RT)^{-1}$ is the constant
11 of the mixture as a characteristic parameter for the mix CO₂(1)/Acetone(2) and $\frac{da}{dT}$ refers to the
12 variational output of enthalpy regards to T.

$$h_{dev} = R.T(1 - Z) + \left(\frac{a_m - T \frac{da}{dT}}{2\sqrt{2}b_m} \right) \ln \left(\frac{Z+2.414B}{Z-0.414B} \right) \quad (36)$$

13

14 The entropy of the mixture (S) has been calculated from the entropy of the corrected ideal mixture,
15 regarding the deviation of the mixture obtained with the Peng-Robinson equation (37). Hence, the
16 entropy of the ideal mixture ($S_{idealmix}$) is calculated with equation (38). In this way, S_i represents the
17 entropy of the ideal gas and X_i the molar fraction of component i in the mixture.

$$S = S_{idealmix} - S_{desv} \quad (36)$$

$$S_{idealmix} = \sum_{i=1}^2 (S_i * x_i) \quad (37)$$

18 Furthermore, the ideal gas entropy of each component can be calculated in the same way from the ideal
19 gas heat capacity ($C_{p_i}^o$) by integration according to expression (39) and the term deviation of entropy
20 (S_{desv}) has been taken from the work of Klein & Nellis, [50] as shown in equation (40)

$$S_i = \int \left(\frac{C_{p_i}^o}{T} \right) * dT \quad (38)$$

$$s_{desv} = -R \cdot \ln(Z - B) - \left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}b_m} \frac{da}{dT} \right) \ln \left(\frac{Z + 2.414B}{Z - 0.414B} \right) \quad (39)$$

1 The calculations of the entropy are as important as the enthalpy since these properties are needed for
 2 the calculation of mass and energy in the simulation of the heat pump.

3 2.5. Compression/resorption heat pump cycle simulation

4 Compression/resorption heat pump cycle simulation is a thermodynamic model based on the mass and
 5 energy balances for each component of the cycle, and on certain typical hypotheses in this type of cycle.
 6 In this sense, figure 1 shows a simplified scheme of the heat pump cycle that operates with the zeotropic
 7 mixture of CO₂/Acetone. The compression/resorption heat pump cycle is made up of a solution circuit
 8 and a vapour line. When using the zeotropic mixture (CO₂/Acetone) the stream leaving the desorber
 9 (stage 4) is a liquid/vapour mixture. This stream is separated at the desorber outlet in the component
 10 defined as "separator" so that the vapour phase stream is directed towards the compressor (stage 5)
 11 while the solution stream (stage 7) is driven by the solution pump to the resorber, previously the solution
 12 passes through the "hot" side of the solution heat exchanger, to increase the temperature of the solution
 13 (stage 8). On the other hand, the vapour stream from the compressor (stage 6) and the stream from the
 14 desorber (stage 9) meet in the component defined as "mixer". The biphasic mixture enters the resorber
 15 (stage 10) where the absorption process is completed with heat dissipation in the sink and leaves the
 16 resorber (stage 11). This stream first passes through the solution heat exchanger, where it preheats the
 17 stream from the desorber, and then through the expansion valve (stage 12). The expansion valve (stage
 18 3) causes a pressure drop in the circuit and consequently an increase in the temperature of the mixture.
 19 Finally, the biphasic solution enters the desorber again and completes the solution circuit.

20
 21

Figure 2. Heat pump cycle

1 Fig. 2 shows a schematic of a compression/resorption heat pump cycle, consisting mainly of a resorption
2 solution circuit (two-phase mixture) and a steam line. The evaporation of the zeotropic mixture in the
3 desorber is not complete, the stream leaving the desorber is a liquid/vapor mixture. This stream is
4 separated, the vapor phase is sent to a mechanically driven compressor while the liquid is recirculated
5 to the resorber (comparable to the condenser in a compression cycle) via a solution pump. The main
6 advantage of compression/resorption cycles involves the better performance due to pressure reduction
7 compared to the compression case using pure refrigerant, and the improvement of cycle efficiency due
8 to lower internal and external temperature gradients in the desorber and reabsorb (Lorentz cycle).
9 Furthermore, the heat production can be varied by changing the concentration of the solution flowing
10 between the desorber and the resorber.

11 The operating conditions of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle are defined by the operating
12 range of its independent variables. The modelling of the cycle is based on the mass and energy balance
13 for each component of the compression/resorption heat pump thermodynamic cycle and a series of
14 conditions of the fluid states at the outlet or inlet of the components. In this sense, to determine these
15 independent variables, it is necessary to show the logical sequence of resolution of the cycle, where
16 table 3 shows the equations of the mass and energy balance for each component of the cycle and table
17 4 the hypotheses assumed for the operation of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle, being the
18 subscript numbering of each point referred to the stages described in figure 2.

19 **Table 3.** Mass and energy balances for each component in the modelling of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle
20 using the CO₂/acetone mixture.

Component of the cycle	Balance equations
Desorber	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $m_{(3)} = m_{l(4)} + m_{v(4)}$ • $m_{(3)}, X_{(3)} = m_{l(4)}, X_{l(4)} + m_{v(4)}, X_{v(4)}$ • $m_{(3)}, h_{(3)} = m_{l(4)}, h_{l(4)} + m_{v(4)}, h_{v(4)}$ • $Q_{des} = m_{(3)} \times (h_{(4)} - h_{(3)})$
Separator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $T_{(4)} = T_{(5)} = T_{(7)}$ • $X_{(7)} = X_{l(4)} = X_{(8)} = X_{(9)}$ • $X_{(5)} = X_{v(4)} = X_{v(6)}$
Pump	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $h_{l(8)} = h_{l(7)} + wp_I$ • $wp_I = [1/\rho_{l(7)} \times (P_{high} - P_{low})] / \mathcal{E}_{pump}$ • $wp = wp_I * m_{l(4)}$
Compressor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $sy_{(6)} = sy_{(5)}$ • $w_{comp} = [m_{v(4)} \times (h_{in(6)} - h_{(5)})] / eff_{comp}$ • $h_{(6)} = h_{(5)} + w_{comp} / m_{v(4)}$
Heat exchanger	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\mathcal{E}_{hex} = (T_{(9)} - T_{(8)}) / (T_{(11)} - T_{(8)})$ • $\mathcal{E}_{hex} = Q_{real} / Q_{max}$ • $Q_{hex} = m_{l(4)} \times (h_{l(9)} - h_{l(8)})$ • $Q_{hex} = m_{(3)} \times (h_{l(11)} - h_{(12)})$
Mixer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $m_{(10)} = m_{l(9)} + m_{v(6)}$ • $m_{(10)}, X_{(10)} = m_{l(9)}, X_{l(9)} + m_{v(6)}, X_{v(6)}$ • $m_{(10)}, h_{(10)} = m_{l(9)}, h_{l(9)} + m_{v(6)}, h_{v(6)}$
Resorber	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $h_{(10)} = (h_{l(9)} + (h_{v(6)} - h_{l(9)})) \times q_{(10)}$ • $m_{(11)} = m_{l(10)} + m_{v(10)}$ • $m_{(11)}, X_{(11)} = m_{l(10)}, X_{l(10)} + m_{v(10)}, X_{v(10)}$ • $m_{(11)}, h_{(11)} = m_{l(10)}, h_{l(10)} + m_{v(10)}, h_{v(10)}$ • $Q_{res} = m_{(10)} \times (h_{(10)} - h_{(11)})$
Expansion valve	<p>For a biphasic mixture:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $h_{(3)} = (h_{l(3)} + (h_{v(3)} - h_{l(3)})) \times q_{(3)}$ • $h_{(3)} = h_{(12)}$

1 Furthermore, the simulation of the heat pump cycle is carried out in a sequential order that allows
 2 relating the mass and energy balance in each component, for which the Engineering Equation Solver
 3 (EES) software was used. The calculated values of the properties of the mixture in the liquid phase and
 4 vapour phase, along with the mass and energy balances in each component and the conditions assumed
 5 by the model that are displayed in table 4. An ideal efficiency was used in the pump, compressor, heat
 6 exchanger and expansion valve to simplify the analysis of the cycle, with the focus of the present work
 7 on the behaviour of the CO₂/acetone mixture when it is used in the compression/resorption heat pump
 8 cycle. In addition, with these assumptions it is expected to obtain a database regarding the
 9 thermodynamic parameters (Pressure, temperature, and composition) in which the cycle using this
 10 mixture is functional.

11 Even more, for the simulation, the independent variables considered for the compression/resorption
 12 heat pump cycle using the CO₂/Acetone mixture are declared in table 5.

13

14 **Table 4.** Hypothetic conditions

Description	Assumed condition
Heat pump cycle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equilibrium in the biphasic mixture • Stages (3); (4); (10) $q=m_v/m_{total}$ • Saturation conditions: Stages (5); (7) (11) • Effectiveness of heat exchanger of the solution $\epsilon_{hex}=1$ • Isentropic performance of the pump $\epsilon_{pump}=1$ • Isentropic performance of compressor $\epsilon_{comp}=1$ • Isenthalpic process in the expansion valve
External circuits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $T_{out_water_resorber} - T_{in_water_resorber} = 5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ • $T_{in_water_desorber} - T_{out_water_desorber} = 5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

15

16 For the assumptions mentioned above, isentropic performance in the pump and the effectiveness in the
 17 heat exchanger are justified in that the mathematical model applied for the simulation is reproducible
 18 and a feasible solution is obtained. For a more realistic simulation, both assumptions can be changed
 19 and the cycle efficiency will decrease. However, it is important to mention that this work is intended to
 20 test whether the CO₂/acetone mixture is suitable for use in a compression/resorption heat pump.

21 In this way, Figure 3 shows the performance of the cycle under standard operating conditions. Here the
 22 following conditions are established as input conditions in the simulation: desorber outlet temperature
 23 of 30°C, resorber outlet temperature of 50°C, overall CO₂ molar concentration difference in the mixture
 24 of 0.10, high pressure of 40 bar and a steam mass flow rate of 1 kg×s⁻¹. The results obtained were: a
 25 temperature difference between the inlet and outlet of the desorber of approximately 15°C, and 10°C
 26 between the inlet and outlet of the resorber. This temperature jump has been taken as a valid case to
 27 continue with new simulation cases.

Figure 3. Initial simulation case study of CO₂/Acetone mixture

Lastly, a combination of the operating intervals of the variables of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle using the CO₂/Acetone mixture allows the determination of the simulation of studies case for the parametric analysis of the cycle. In this sense, table 5 presents a summary of the study cases determined by varying the temperature of the solution at the desorber outlet from 30 to 70°C with increments of 20°C, ΔX between 0.10 and 0.20 with increments of 0.05, the temperature of the solution at the resorber outlet from 50 to 110°C with increments of 10°C, high pressure in the heat pump cycle between 30 and 50 bar with increments of 10 bar and a vapour mass flow value of 0.5 and 1 kg/s, where:

- $T_{(4)}$: Desorber outlet temperature – solution side
- $T_{(11)}$: Resorber outlet temperature – solution side
- $\Delta X = X_{global} - X_i$: Composition difference between the global concentration of CO₂ in the mixture and poor solution
- P_{high} : Heat pump cycle high pressure
- \dot{m}_v : Vapour mass flow

Table 5. Parameter for the simulation of the heat pump cycle compression/resorption using CO₂/acetone mixture

P_{high} 30 Bar					
T₍₄₎ 30C°					
ΔX 10		ΔX 15		ΔX 20	
T₍₁₁₎	\dot{m}_v	T₍₁₁₎	\dot{m}_v	T₍₁₁₎	\dot{m}_v
C°	kg×s⁻¹	C°	kg×s⁻¹	C°	kg×s⁻¹
50	0.5	50	0.5	50	0.5
50	1	50	1	50	1
60	0.5	60	0.5	60	0.5
60	1	60	1	60	1
70	0.5	70	0.5	70	0.5
70	1	70	1	70	1

P_{high} 40 Bar					
T₍₄₎ 50C°					
ΔX 10		ΔX 15		ΔX 20	
T_(II)	\dot{m}_v	T_(II)	\dot{m}_v	T_(II)	\dot{m}_v
C°	kg×s⁻¹	C°	kg×s⁻¹	C°	kg×s⁻¹
70	0.5	70	0.5	70	0.5
70	1	70	1	70	1
80	0.5	80	0.5	80	0.5
80	1	80	1	80	1
90	0.5	90	0.5	90	0.5
90	1	90	1	90	1
P_{high} 50 Bar					
T₍₄₎ 70C°					
ΔX 10		ΔX 15		ΔX 20	
T_(II)	\dot{m}_v	T_(II)	\dot{m}_v	T_(II)	\dot{m}_v
C°	kg×s⁻¹	C°	kg×s⁻¹	C°	kg×s⁻¹
90	0.5	90	0.5	90	0.5
90	1	90	1	90	1
100	0.5	100	0.5	100	0.5
100	1	100	1	100	1
110	0.5	110	0.5	110	0.5
110	1	110	1	110	1

1

2 Table 5 shows that for each high-pressure value of the cycle (30, 40 and 50 bar), two study cases have
3 been defined with respect to the vapour mass flow rate, of these three study cases are determined
4 concerning the temperature of the solution at the outlet of the resorber as a boundary condition, the
5 difference in composition between the global concentration of CO₂ in the mixture and lean solution and
6 the temperature of the solution at the outlet of the desorber. In this way, regarding different temperatures
7 on the desorber (30, 50 and 70°C) and the difference composition of CO₂ concentration (10, 15 and 20
8 ΔX) there are 18 possible combinations for each high pressure of the cycle (30, 40 and 50 bar), the total
9 number of cases studied is 54. Furthermore, the energy efficiency of this equipment is characterized
10 through the Operating Coefficient (COP) defined as the ratio of the heat produced Q₂ divided by the
11 work consumed W. The energy balance in the heat pump allows us to relate the energy exchanges in
12 form of heat and work that take place, Q₁ + W = Q₂, and the COP = Q₂/W [54].

13

14

15 3. Results and discussion

16

17 Following the methodology expressed by previous research that used the Peng-Robinson equations and
18 correlated its findings, it was possible to determine a model of the properties and thermodynamic cycle
19 of a thermal pump based on a mixture of CO₂ / Acetone. In this sense, the following sub-themes present
20 the results obtained.

21 3.1. Parameters of binary interaction for the mixture CO₂/Acetone

22

23 Through the realization of the adjustment of the database available and the calculations with the Peng-
24 Robinson equations for the mixture CO₂ / Acetone, the parameters of binary interaction for different
25 temperatures were obtained and are presented in table 6 and table 7 the results for the coefficients k₁,
26 k₂ and k₃ found are presented.

1

2 **Table 6.** *K₁₂ parameters for different temperatures*

Temperature (K)	<i>K₁₂</i>
291.15	-0.00516
298.15	0.01097
303.15	0.00794
313.15	-0.00630
333.15	-0.05077
353.15	-0.11221
373.15	-0.17869
393.15	-0.23040

3

4

5 **Table 7.** *k coefficients for binary interaction parameters*

Temperature (K)	k1	k2	k3
291.15 – 393.15	1.1139x10 ⁻⁴	8.501x10 ⁻⁶	-2.851x10 ⁻³

6

7 The results obtained when using these coefficients in the calculation of compositions of the liquid and
8 vapor phases, were compared with the experimental ones of Hsieh & Vrabec, [40], Chiu et al., [41]
9 and Han et al., [39], obtaining a maximum mean square deviation of 4.28 %, 6.91 % and 8.70 %, respectively.
10 The comparison of the data obtained through the use of these coefficients (Eq. (20)) in the
11 present work with those obtained experimentally in the cited works, is shown in the graphs provided in
12 appendix B.

13 Regarding the density of the mixture in the liquid phases, the results obtained with the model were
14 compared with the experimental ones obtained by Ramírez-Ramos et al., [42], obtaining a maximum
15 square deviation of 13.4 %. The data fit for the density in the liquid phase of the mixture was improved
16 using the Peneloux specific volume correction term [52]. In this case, the maximum square deviation
17 values of 2.45 % and 4.11 % for the liquid phase and vapour, respectively. Regarding the deviation
18 found between experimental data and those calculated for the excess enthalpy data of Ramírez-Ramos
19 et al., a maximum deviation of 5.35 % was obtained.

20

21 **3.2. Vapour Pressure diagram**

22

23 The graphic of vapour pressure is also known as the diagram of VLE or bell, regarding the results
24 obtained in different temperatures, figure 4 displays the pressure of the liquid-saturated vapour phases
25 of the CO₂ / Acetone mixture as a function of the CO₂ composition from 0.10 in mole fraction to pure
26 CO₂ from 15°C to 120°C of temperature. Each point on the graph represents a case of vapor-liquid
27 equilibrium for a given temperature, pressure, and CO₂ composition in the CO₂/acetone mixture.

Figure 4. Vapour Pressure of CO₂/Acetone mixtures against CO₂ mass fraction at different temperatures calculated with Peng-Robinson EoS

It is shown that the pressure rises constantly as the molar composition of CO₂ in the mixture increases until it reaches the critical point at each temperature. From the critical point found there is a sudden drop in the composition corresponding to the saturated vapour phase, the increment of pressure with the increase of CO₂ is possible due to the critical pressure difference between the two compounds, meaning that a greater critical pressure allows to reach higher pressures until it drops. This behaviour has a similarity to the research performed by Bamberger & Maurer [55], who compared the CO₂/Acetone mixture from several research. The data obtained for the graph show that the minimum - maximum value of pressure and temperature at which the mixture is in liquid and saturated vapour are 12 - 120 bar and 15 - 120°C, respectively. The minimum global composition of CO₂ to obtain saturated vapour is 0.75 at 120°C, this concentration value rises to values close to 1 if the temperature decreases to a minimum of 15°C. The top moves to the right to decrease the equilibrium temperature of the CO₂ / Acetone mixture Fabian et al., [56] carried out an analysis of acetone dissolved in CO₂ in 11 different compositions in a range of temperatures from 50 to 100 K close to the critical point. Here it was found that the critical temperature of the mixture changes in direct relation to the composition, likewise the critical pressure reaches a maximum around the value of the acetone mole fraction of 0.3, and the critical density could also present a maximum molar fraction of 0.2 of acetone. In addition, this work validates the applicability of molecular modelling for the determination of the vapor-liquid equilibrium in CO₂/acetone mixtures. The equilibrium results of this work (Pressure, composition, and temperature) have been compared with those of the present research. In this way, the comparison denotes an average standard deviation of 10% has been obtained with respect to the pressure in a composition of 0.40 to 0.90 of CO₂ dissolved in Acetone in a temperature range between 298 and 393 K. This shows that the correlation obtained for the present work corresponds to other investigations that have studied the behaviour of the CO₂/Acetone mixture under different conditions of pressure, composition, and temperature.

On the other hand, based on the Clausius-Clapeyron equation, the Duhring diagram of the CO₂ / Acetone mixture is made, where figure 5 shows the graphical representation of the vapour pressure versus $(-T) \cdot 1000; T$ in K, for different compositions of the liquid phase and saturated vapour. This diagram of Duhring is particularly useful when representing the thermodynamic cycle of the heat pump because it allows for visualizing the values of the pressures, temperatures and compositions of the cycle

1 currents operating with the working mixture. In this way, knowing the operation conditions of CO₂,
 2 allows to determinate how the fluid will behave on the cycle regarding the need of separate one
 3 compound from other by vaporization.

4
 5 **Figure 5.** Diagram PTXY (Duhring) of CO₂/Acetone mixture

6 **3.3. Density**

7
 8 The calculation of the density of the compound required the coefficients of the correlation of
 9 experimental data expressed in table 8. In this sense, the molar fraction of the CO₂ in the expression
 10 X_{CO_2} retrieves the following coefficients required in equation (26).

11 **Table 8.** Coefficient of correlation

Coefficient	Value
ρ_{00}	0.5439
ρ_{10}	0.08759
ρ_{01}	0.2207
ρ_{20}	0.02544
ρ_{11}	0.107
ρ_{02}	0.09804
ρ_{21}	0.03737
ρ_{12}	0.1037
ρ_{03}	0.08257

12

13 The results obtained with the Peng-Robinson equation of state regarding the density of the CO₂/Acetone
 14 mixture in the liquid and vapour phases were compared with the experimental data obtained by
 15 Ramírez-Ramos et al., [42]. In this sense, a maximum, medium and minimum deviation of 13.4, 5.2
 16 and 2.4 %, respectively was obtained, and by using these three values, obtaining a better adjustment
 17 The data for the density in the liquid phase of the mixture was improved using the Pénélox volume
 18 correction term [52], being in this case the maximum, medium and minimum deviation values of 2.5,
 19 1.8 and 0.8 % for the liquid and 4.1, 3.2 and 1.2 % for the vapour phase. Furthermore, Fig. 6 shows the
 20 comparison of the density data in the liquid phase of the CO₂/ Acetone mixture obtained by Ramírez-
 21 Ramos et al., [42], with the model established in the present work. That comparison was made over a
 22 temperature range between 18 and 120 °C, a CO₂ mole fraction of 0.05 to 0.814, and pressure between
 23 0.03 and 8.715 MPa.

Figure 6. Comparison (Model-Experimental) of CO₂/acetone mixture density data

On the other hand, the excess enthalpy values have been calculated with the Peng-Robinson equation of state and have been compared with the experimental data presented by Ramírez-Ramos et al., [42] in the defined range of pressure, temperature and molar composition of CO₂ in the CO₂/Acetone mixture. From this comparison, a maximum, medium and minimum deviation of 5.4, 3.5 and 1.3 %, respectively, have been obtained.

3.4. Parametric study

The equations described from 2.1 to 2.4 are taken from existing equations of state, however it has been determined that the Peng - Robinson equation of state is the most suitable due to a smaller deviation between experimental and simulation data by the approximation cited in 3.1 to 3.3

The parametric analysis of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle using the CO₂/Acetone mixture has been developed to analyse the influence of the independent variables of the cycle when one of them remains constant. This analysis makes it possible to determine the behaviour of the CO₂/Acetone mixture in this type of heat pump cycles. The mixture constitutes a new working fluid for this type of application, thus extending the use of this zeotropic mixture.

In this way, the results that are presented as follows comes from the software simulations which represent a presents clear tendency of a decreasing COP at higher temperatures. Regarding the validity of using computational simulations, the research of Cao et al. [56] on the utilization of zeotropic mixtures for an enhanced heat pump simulated with MATLAB has a response with the same tendency of COP vs condenser temperature, showing an important agreement with experimental results, meaning reliability on the simulated results. In this sense, the COP results of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle at a resorber outlet solution temperature between 50 and 70°C, ΔX between 0.10 and 0.20, for an outlet solution temperature of the desorber (T_{des}) at 30°C, at a pressure of a) 30, b) 40 and c) 50 bar. The figure of this results can be found on appendix A under figure A1 and shows that if the high pressure of the cycle is constant and the temperature of the solution at the outlet of the resorber is 50°C, the value of the operating coefficient reaches the higher conditions up to a maximum of 3. If P_{high} increases its value from 30 to 50 bar, the value of the heat pump cycle operation coefficient decreases to a minimum value of 1.01, a thermal jump of 20°C and an increasing ΔX from 0.10 to 0.20 increases the value of COP. Furthermore, it was found that the value of the vapour mass flow rate (\dot{m}_v) does not influence the determination of the heat pump cycle operation coefficient, since the calculated COP values are superimposed on the graph.

1 On the other hand, the results of the heat pump cycle operation coefficient with a solution temperature
2 at the desorber outlet of 50°C, with a solution temperature at the resorber outlet between 70 and 90°C,
3 ΔX between 0.10 and 0.20 at a pressure of a) 30, b) 40 and c) 50 bar is displayed on figure A2 from
4 appendix A. In this way, this figure shows that the COP values decrease to values close to 1 when the
5 temperature of the solution at the outlet of the resorber increases from 70 to 90°C. The highest value of
6 COP, in this case, is 2.10, this is obtained with a value of ΔX of 0.20, a temperature of the solution at
7 the outlet of the resorber of 70°C at a pressure of 50 bar. If the cycle high pressure increases from 30 to
8 40 bar, the value of the heat pump cycle operation coefficient is reduced when $\Delta X = 0.10$. However, for
9 $\Delta X = 0.15$ and 0.20, it is shown that for a value of P_{high} between 40 and 50 bar, the value of COP can be
10 found from null to very close to 1 when there is a temperature jump between source and sink of 30°C
11 or higher. It has been determined that under these conditions the cycle does not operate as a
12 compression/resorption heat pump when using the CO₂/acetone mixture as the working fluid.

13 Furthermore, figure A3 from appendix A shows the COP values determined when the temperature of
14 the solution at the outlet of the desorber is 70°C, a temperature of the solution at the outlet of the resorber
15 between 90 and 110°C, ΔX between 0.10 and 0.20, at a pressure of a) 30, b) 40 and c) 50 bar. In this
16 way, the results shows that at a 30 bar heat pump cycle P_{high} the COP values have been determined only
17 when ΔX is between 0.10 and 0.15, at ΔX of 0.20 the solution is in a state of saturation. The highest
18 calculated COP value is 2, this is obtained with a high cycle pressure of 40 bar, a solution temperature
19 at the resorber outlet of 90°C and ΔX is 0.20. It has been determined that a temperature jump between
20 the heat source and the sink of 20 °C and 30°C is feasible for the compression/resorption heat pump
21 cycle, with a heat source temperature of 70°C at a high cycle pressure of 40 bar, except for $\Delta X = 0.10$.
22 In this way, the results of the operation coefficient show a better performance of the
23 compression/resorption heat pump cycle with a high pressure between 30 and 40 bar. A solution
24 temperature at the desorber outlet of 30°C improves the efficiency of the cycle, up to a maximum value
25 of $COP_{max}=3$. If the largest thermal jump determined between the heat source and sink of the
26 compression/resorption heat pump cycle using the CO₂/acetone mixture is 20°C, the value of the cycle
27 operation coefficient is increased until reaching the highest values, determined at each high pressure of
28 the cycle. It has been determined that it is possible to generate heat pump cycle sink temperature by
29 compression/resorption using the CO₂/acetone mixture of up to 100°C with a source temperature of
30 70°C, a difference between global composition and a lean composition (ΔX) of 0.20 and an P_{high} at 40
31 bar. In the same way, is important to mention the stability presented in the CO₂ concentration, compared
32 to the research of Pan et al. that analysed the behaviour of the 4 zeotropic mixtures of CO₂ with the
33 refrigerants R32, R134a, R152a and R290 on a regenerative supercritical CO₂ Bryton Cycle, that
34 showed that the mass fraction of CO₂ provoke a decrement on the COP as it increased until reaching a
35 lower state and then it starts to grow [28]. In this sense, the present system shows that for almost every
36 condition, a greater CO₂ concentration means better performance, making it more reliable to predict its
37 behaviour.

38 Moreover, a summary of the calculated values of the coefficient of operation (COP) as a function of the
39 temperature of the solution at the desorber outlet (30, 50 and 70°C), the temperature of the solution at
40 the outlet of the resorber between (50 and 100°C), a vapour mass flow rate (\dot{m}_v) of 0.5 and 1 kg/s, ΔX
41 between 0.10 and 0.20, at a pressure of 30, 40 and 50 bar, are presented in the figure 5: a, b and c,
42 respectively. In this way, figure 7.a shows that the coefficient of operation of the heat pump cycle (COP)
43 decreases from 3 to 1.2 when the temperature of the solution at the desorber outlet increases from 30 to
44 50°C. It is observed that the best performance of the cycle occurs when the difference in composition
45 between the global concentration of CO₂ in the mixture and lean solution (ΔX) has a value between
46 0.15 and 0.20. The operating coefficient of the heat pump cycle decreases when the temperature of the
47 solution at the outlet of the resorber increases from 50 to 100°C. The effect of the vapour mass flow rate
48 is not relevant since the COP values overlap for both cases (0.5 and 1 kg×s⁻¹).

1 On the other hand, figure 7.b shows that if the high pressure of the cycle is 40 bar, the coefficient of
 2 operation of the heat pump cycle (COP) decreases when the temperature of the solution at the desorber
 3 outlet increases from 30 to 70°C. The values of the coefficient of operation of the heat pump cycle
 4 increase to a maximum value of 2.8 with $\Delta X = 0.20$. The COP of the cycle is reduced to a minimum
 5 value of 1.01 when the temperature of the solution at the outlet of the resorber increases from 50 to
 6 70°C, this happens at $\Delta X=0.10$. It is shown that a thermal revaluation is feasible from a source
 7 temperature of 70°C to a sink temperature of 100°C. Furthermore, the research developed by Moreira
 8 Da-silva et al. [57] presented similar modelling of the compression/resorption cycle of the mixture
 9 CO₂/Acetone for air-conditioning in typical thermal conditions, where the temperature at the resorber
 10 outlet was 35°C and two cases were considered the first with $\Delta X=0.2$ and the second with $\Delta X=0.3$,
 11 regarding the same $P_{high} = 40$ in both cases, leading to a COP of 3.58 for case 1 and 2.71 for case 2 [57].
 12 In this way, it can be seen that at $\Delta X=0.2$ the COP of the two models is similar in that it was proven
 13 that a higher temperature at the desorber outlet means a lower COP, and even more, the difference
 14 between a poor and a rich mixture has an impact that is shown in the great COP of $\Delta X=0.3$.

15 Furthermore, figure 7.c shows that the heat pump cycle operating coefficient (COP) decreases when the
 16 temperature of the solution at the desorber outlet increases by 30 to 70°C at a high pressure of 50 bar.
 17 A composition difference between the global concentration of CO₂ in the mixture and poor solution ΔX
 18 = 0.20 increases the values of the operating coefficient of the heat pump cycle (COP), up to a maximum
 19 of COP=2.6. If the temperature of the solution at the outlet of the resorber increases from 50 to 100°C,
 20 the COP of the cycle drops to a minimum value of 1.1. The maximum temperature of the solution at the
 21 outlet of the resorber for these conditions, where the cycle works as a heat pump, is 100°C at a pressure
 22 of 40 bar.

23

24

a)

b)

c)

Figure 7. COP at a P_{high} at a) 30 bar b) 40 bar c) 50 bar

Globally, if the temperature of the solution at the outlet of the desorber increases from 30 °C to 70 °C at the same pressure value, the performance of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle decreases from a maximum value from 3 to 1.1. The best global performance of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle occurs with a range of Δx (Composition difference between the global concentration of CO₂ in the mixture and poor solution) between 0.15 and 0.20. If the high cycle pressure increases, the cycle performance decreases. On the other hand, if the temperature of the solution at the outlet of the resorber increases along with the temperature at the outlet of the desorber, the performance of the cycle decreases. In this way, it is shown that the variation in the vapour mass flow from 0.5 to 1 kg \times s⁻¹ does not affect the operating coefficient of the cycle, since the results overlap with each other.

This phenomenon was also observed in the research of Gao et al. who reports that the elevated temperature results in an increment of the ratio pressure and discharge temperature of the system leading to a deterioration of the performance on the compression cycle [13]. In this sense, it is recommended that the solution temperature at the outlet of the desorber not exceed 40°C and a break of this with the sink temperature of 20°C. Furthermore, when comparing the utilization of transcritical CO₂ on water heating applications, it has been found by F. Cao et al. [58] on experiments with internal heat

1 exchangers and conditions of ambient, water inlet and water outlet temperature of 16; 10 and 70°C
 2 respectively, that the COP reaches a value of 3.76 without heat exchanger and 3.81 with heat exchanger.
 3 In this way, experimentally, using transcritical CO₂ bring a better COP than the best CO₂/Acetone
 4 mixture of 3.58. However, the presented zeotropic mixture allows to operate on subcritical conditions,
 5 allowing to reduce prices on equipment for lower pressures, granting at the same time acceptable COP
 6 values.

7 On the other hand, another important parameter that denotes the performance of the heat pump cycle is
 8 the ratio flow rate between the poor solution and that of the refrigerant expressed as ($f = \dot{m}_l / \dot{m}_v$). In
 9 this way, the ratio flow rate when the high pressure in the cycle is 30 bar has the highest calculated
 10 values ($f = 7.1$) with a composition difference between the global concentration of CO₂ in the mixture
 11 and poor solution (ΔX) of 0.10 is displayed in figure 8.a, showing that the solution temperature at the
 12 desorber outlet has a very slight influence on the ratio flow rate. The solution temperature at the resorber
 13 outlet is also not a variable that considerably influences the ratio flow rate. The values range in which
 14 the flow rate ratio is found for this pressure (30 bar) is between 3 and 7.1. The effect of the rate vapour
 15 mass flow is not relevant since the COP values overlap for both cases (0.5 and $1 \text{ kg}\times\text{s}^{-1}$).

16 The highest ratio of solution value and rates vapour flow in the cycle for high pressure of 40 bars $f =$
 17 6.8 as shown in figure 8.b, this is obtained in the same way as for a 30 bar P_{high} with $\Delta X = 0.10$. The
 18 range of values in which the ratio flow rate is found for this pressure (40 bar) is between 3 to 6.8.
 19 Comparing this interval of “ f ” with that determined for a P_{high} in the 30 bar heat pump cycle, a reduction
 20 between its higher and lower limits is shown.

21 The ratio of solution and vapour flows of the cycle at a pressure of 50 bar reaches a value $f = 6.2$ in
 22 figure 8.c, this is also determined with $\Delta X = 0.10$, as in the cases with P_{high} of 30 and 40 bar. The range
 23 of values in which the ratio flow rate is found for this pressure (40 bar) is between 2.5 to 6.2. On the
 24 other hand, the temperature of the solution at the outlet of the desorber, the temperature of the solution
 25 at the outlet of the resorber and the rate mass flow of vapour do not strongly influence the ratio flow
 26 rate f .

a)

b)

c)

Figure 8. Flow rate ratio (f) at a high cycle pressure of a) 30 bar b) 40 bar c) 50 bar

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In general, the values calculated for the ratio flow rate are in the range between 2.5 and 7.1 minimum and maximum, respectively. The highest calculated values for the ratio flow rate f occur when ΔX is 0.10. The increase in high pressure in the cycle represents a decrease in the flow rate ratio. The variation in the rate vapour mass flow from 0.5 to 1 $\text{kg} \times \text{s}^{-1}$ does not affect the calculated ratio flow rate since the results overlap with each other. However, it's important to mention that regarding the increment on rate pressure flow also become lower, in this sense, the research of Jensen et al., on the development of absorption-compression heat pumps based on ammonia-water mixtures, concluded that for circulating ratios lower than 0.5 and rich concentrations of ammonia between 0.2 and 0.8 resulted on a considerable increment on the ratio pressure, which at the same time produced a reduction on the COP, making this kind of design not recommendable [27]. In this way, is important to consider the pressure proportions, mass friction and its results in flow ratio to maximize the enhancement of the COP on the system.

3.5 Comparison of results of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle using the CO₂/acetone mixtures with related investigations

In a comparative way, a literature review was performed with related works on heat pumps that use CO₂ as a pure refrigerant (transcritical cycle) as well as combined with absorbents, to show a comparison of the data results obtained in the simulation of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle using the CO₂/Acetone mixture, which is displayed on Table 9.

Table 9. Comparison of results of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle using the CO₂/acetone mixtures with related investigations

Reference	Description of work / product	Fluid	Fluid and Temp. at heat source (°C)	Fluid and temperature achieved (°C)	Power (kW)	COP
Present work [-]	Modeling of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle using the CO ₂ /Acetone mixture.	CO ₂ /Acetone	Waste water 30 a 70	Water 50 a 100	100 a 250	1.1 a 3
Mayekawa [69]	CO ₂ transcritical heat pumps.. Eco Sirocco	CO ₂ transc. (R744)	Waste water 20 - 25	Air 100-120	65 a 90	2.9
Durr Therme CO ₂ [70]	Heat pump Thermeco2 HHR1000	CO ₂ transc. (R744)	Waste water 8 a 40	Water 80- 110	51 a 2.2 MW	3.9
Kobe Steel – Kobelco [71]	Semi-hermetic twin-screw inverter for industrial applications	R134a y R245fa Mixture	Air 10 a 40	Water 90	70 a 230	1.7 a 3
Ochsner Energie Technik GmbH [22]	Heat pump, model: IWWSS R2R3b	R134a y OK01 Mixture	Waste water 35 a 55	Water 95 a 130	170 a 750	5.3
Mitsubishi [72]	Compact hot water heat pump with closed economizer and a two-stage turbocharger with intermediate injection. Model: ETW- L	R134 a	Waste water 10 a 50	Water 90	340 a 600	4.1

Considering the operating temperature range of the present work, it is shown to be one of the widest (30 to 70 °C) with reference to the temperature in the heat source compared to the other studies.

1 Regarding the temperature in the sink, it is shown that the range determined between 50 and 100 °C for
2 this work has a range quite similar to that of the Durr Thermea CO₂ company [61], Kobe Steel - Kobelco
3 [62] and Mitsubishi [64], considering that in all three works, the fluid to be heated is water. The range
4 of calorific power calculated for the present work (100 to 250 kW) is very close to that presented in the
5 work of the company Kobe Steel - Kobelco [62], which indicates that this technology is viable for its
6 implementation using the CO₂/acetone mixture. Finally, the results obtained for the performance of the
7 cycle show that the compression/resorption heat pump cycle using the CO₂/acetone mixture as working
8 fluid is viable. The COP range calculated for this work is 1.1 to 3, this depends, as has been seen, on
9 the conditions of temperature, pressure and molar composition of CO₂ in the CO₂/acetone mixture,
10 where the cycle of the heat pump is operated. Furthermore, it can be considered that this range of COP
11 is an average value for the ranges calculated by the works developed in the companies Mayekawa [60]
12 of 2.9, Durr Thermea CO₂ [61] of 3.9, Kobe Steel - Kobelco [62] between 1.7 and 3, and Mitsubishi
13 [64] of 4.1. The highest efficiency recorded for a water heat pump cycle is the one presented by the
14 company Ochsner Energie Technik GmbH [63] when using the R134a Mix + OK01 mix as working pair,
15 the COP reaches a value of 5.3.

17 4. Conclusions

18
19 The modelling of the utilization of a novel mixture of CO₂/acetone as a working fluid for
20 compression/resorption heat pump is a technology that allows to move to non-hazardous and eco-
21 friendly alternatives. In this research it was modelled this application on operative conditions of low
22 heat waste exploitation showing promising results such as congruence with the literature and coefficient
23 of performance increment under certain parameters.

24 The Peng Robinson equation of state was selected as the method to determine the equilibrium and other
25 thermodynamic properties of the mixture. In this sense, it was used following the methodology of
26 several authors, proving to be useful and the results validate its use for the CO₂/acetone mixture. In this
27 way, the adjustment of equilibrium parameters of the CO₂/acetone mixture between experimental data
28 obtained in the literature and calculated showed a maximum average square deviation of 4.28 % and
29 8.70 % for a temperature range between 291 to 303 K and 333 to 393 K, respectively. Even more, the
30 calculation of the polynomial equation for the binary interaction parameter (k_{12}) in the model based on
31 the cubic Peng Robinson equation of state showed that the most influential parameter for the fit is k_1 .

32 On the other hand, the independent variables of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle and its
33 operating range were determined by the range of experimental data found in the literature and the range
34 was determined by the vapour pressure diagram of the mixture. In this way, the modelling of the heat
35 pump cycle was based on the adjustment of matter and energy of each component of the cycle and a
36 hypothetical assumption of the state of the mixture at different points of the cycle in a simulated study
37 case.

38 The analysis of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle using the CO₂/acetone mixture defines a
39 range of CO₂ concentrations of 20 to 50 %. In this sense, a higher molar concentration of CO₂ improves
40 the efficiency of the compression/resorption heat pump cycle, reaching heating temperatures in the sink
41 up to 110 °C. Furthermore, if the temperature of the solution at the desorber outlet increases from 30 °C
42 to 70 °C, the cycle efficiency (COP) decreases from a value of 3 to 1.1. Even more, it was defined that
43 the increase in high pressure (30 to 50 bar) is a determining parameter in cycle performance (COP).

44 On the other hand, the highest value of the operation coefficient of the compression/resorption heat
45 pump cycle (COP=3) was determined when the composition difference between the global
46 concentration of CO₂ in the mixture and poor solution (ΔX) is 0.20, the temperature of the solution at
47 the outlet of the desorber is 30 °C and the difference in temperature between source and sink is 20 °C.

1 An important point to mention is that the COP value obtained in the cycle simulation was not affected
2 by the variation of the steam mass flow rate.

3 Lastly, the flow rate ratio in the compression/resorption heat pump cycle showed to increase in value if
4 the solution temperature at the desorber and resorber outlets increases from 30 to 70 °C and 50 to 110
5 °C, respectively. In this way, the highest value calculated in the flow rate ratio was 7.1, this value was
6 determined at a molar concentration difference of CO₂ between the mixture line and the solution line
7 (ΔX) of 0.10. The variable with the greatest influence on the flow rate ratio is the difference in molar
8 concentration of CO₂ in the CO₂/Acetone mixture between the mixing line and the solution line.

9 On the other hand, the present modelling investigation reflected the parametric simulation to the
10 construction and experimentation of a application model that has been developed on a continuous
11 research that considers the effects of a heat exchanger.

12

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14

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18

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29 **6. Appendix A**
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Figure A.1. The temperature at resorber outlet is between 50 °C and 70°C; The temperature at desorber is 30 °C and the high pressure is of a)30 b)40 and c)50 bars

b)

c)

Figure A 2. The temperature at resorber outlet is between 70 °C and 90°C; The temperature at the desorber is 50 °C and the high pressure is of a)30 b)40 and 50 bars

a)

b)

c)

1 **Figure A 3.** The temperature at resorber outlet is between 90°C to 110; The temperature at desorber is 70 °C and the high
 2 pressure is of a)30 b)40 and 50 bars

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6 **2. Appendix B**

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5 **Figure A 4.** Comparison of data obtained with experimental data by Hsieh & Vrabec [40] of CO2
 6 mass fraction in liquid phase and vapour phase of CO2/acetone mixture

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5 **Figure A 5.** Comparison of data obtained with experimental data by Chiu et al., [41] of CO₂ mass
6 fraction in liquid and vapor phase of CO₂/acetone mixture.

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Figure A 6. Comparison of data obtained with experimental data by Han et al., [39] of CO2 mass fraction in liquid phase and vapour phase of CO2/acetone mixture,